

Paper 4

A STUDY OF SOCIAL ATTITUDE IN TECHNO-BASED MATHEMATICAL LEARNING AND NON-TECHNO BASED MATHEMATICS LEARNING OF 9TH STANDARD STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Attitudes are associations between attitude objects (Virtually any aspect of the social world) and evaluations of those objects (Fazio & Roskos Ewolsen, 1994). More simply attitudes are lasting evaluations of various aspects of the social world-evaluations that are stored in memory (Judd et al, 1991). The study of social attitudes of people has gained prime importance. Attitudes us the governing tendencies of human behaviour, occupy a place of fundamental importance in the field of social psychology. A man’s total behaviour is the reflection of his deep underlying attitudes which are the controlling forces in all our motions.

The psychologist, therefore, is rightly prompted to regard the study of social attitudes as the central problem of social psychology. Clark (1924), stated that the study of social attitudes “should become one of the primary objectives of social psychological effort”. The main purpose of Information and communication technology (ICT) in Education means implementing ICT Equipments and Tools in Teaching-Learning process as a media and methodology and to familiarize students with the use and workings of computers. Information and communication technology has connected the world including students throughout world and it has become the central drive for the evolution of a modern society. ICT are being used more and more as part of learning processes in both formal and informal settings. The Information and communication technology has witnessed a fast growth and has changed traditional form of libraries to digital form. Information and communication technology are a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate, and to create, disseminate, store, and manage information.

Communication and information are at the very heart of the educational process, consequently ICT-use in education has a long history. At present throughout world, the most popular source of information is the internet and e-resources. In the present study, conducted in Kozhikode district in Kerala state, quantitative approach with survey design was used. The survey included 100 ninth standard students selected at random from two educational institutions of the Kozhikode district. It is noted that statistically, non-significant difference was observed between male and female respondents towards social attitude and the use of e-resources for learning and entertainment purpose. The study further revealed that there is a significant difference between the variables.

Keywords: Social attitude, Information and communication technologies (ICT), attitude towards ICT, Achievement in mathematics.

1.0.0. Introduction

Social psychology is the scientific field that seeks to understand the nature and causes of individual behaviour and thought in social situations in other words, social psychology seeks to understand how we think about and interact with others. The topics that social psychological study are very different from those in the physical or biological sciences, the methods we employ are similar in nature and orientation. For this reason, it makes sense to describe social psychology as basically scientific in nature. Use of Technology in mathematics had begun with the use of tangible material like abacus. Technology can reduce the task of tedious computations and instead enhance students' focus on important mathematical concepts. Technology can represent mathematics in ways that help students understand the concepts understanding of mathematics. Also, these features can enable teachers to reflect and improve both how and what students learn. The tools of technology help students to think in abstract terms and translate these abstract ideas into a tangible form. In this regard techno-based tools provide a perfectly tangible form above primary level (Kaput, 1992; Kaput 2007). But Information and communication technology can be supportive only when appropriate technology and pedagogy integration has taken place, where pedagogy includes the teaching techniques tools of assessment, as well as curriculum (Means & Haertel, 2004). The present study is largely concerned with understanding the social attitude of techno-based mathematics learners and non-techno based mathematics learners of ninth standard students and how they handle the digitalization process and what results come out of it. There is still limited knowledge about how to exploit information and communication technologies and successfully

integrate them into education to support teaching and improve students’ conditions for learning. This study aims to increase such understanding by examining the social attitude of techno-based mathematical learners and non-techno based mathematics learners of 9th standard students.

1.1.0. Need for the study

The purpose of the study was to find out the social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students. Social Attitude were measured with the help of five psychological variables; Attitude towards teachers and parents, attitude towards discipline, attitude towards life and humanity, attitude towards country and attitude towards religion. There is a paradigm shift in education system in India in terms of the educational practices integrating ICT with the teaching and learning environment. In the present times when the information is available by the click of the mouse still the students are unable to convert this abundant information into knowledge. This is because of lack of positive techno-based education attitude among students. Techno-based education improves engagement and knowledge retention: When techno-based education is integrated with mathematics learning, students become more engaged in their learning process. This is because technology provides different opportunities to make mathematics more fun and enjoyable in terms of teaching the same things in different ways. This study evaluates the social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students.

1.2.0 Statement of the Problem

A study of social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students

1.3.0. Operational definitions of the key terms

Information and communication technology (ICT)

“Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is defined as all devices, tools, content, resources, forums, and services, digital and those that can be converted into or delivered through digital forums, which can be deployed for realising the goals of teaching learning, enhancing access to and reach of resources, building of capacities, as well as management of the educational system.” as given by National Policy on Information and Communication Technology in School Education. It is not restricted to hardware or software devices only, but it also includes interactive

medium like satellite communication devices, open educational resources, television and radio services, internet etc.

Attitude

Attitude refers to a learned tendency of a person to respond positively or negatively towards an object, situation, a concept, or a person. It is also regarded as a belief held by individuals that reflects their opinions and feelings and can be sometimes manifested in behaviour (Joseph, 2013). Attitudes, behaviour, and feelings are interrelated in such a way that people's attitudes determine their behaviour towards objects, situations, and people. They also influence the relationships that exist among these variables with themselves (Joseph, 2013). Attitudes are not innate; they are learned or acquired via socialization and vary between groups and individuals depending on different cultural factors, and as a result of each subjects' various experiences. Attitudes are general evaluations that people hold regarding a particular entity, such as an object, an issue, or a person or a subject. Attitude towards ICT includes different dimensions namely attitude towards ICT, Perception of ICT, e-learning, internet usage, mobile learning and Social media.

Social attitude

A social attitude was defined as "a behaviour pattern, anticipatory set or tendency, predisposition to specific adjustment or more simply, a conditioned response to social stimuli" (Dockery & Bedeian).

Achievement in mathematics

Achievement in mathematics is the capability to achieve mathematically. It is reflected by the percentage of marks obtained in Class 8th and 9th mathematics examination conducted by Kerala state board. High Achievers: High achievers are those whose scores academic performance is above average. Low Achievers: Low achievers are those whose scores academic performance is below average.

1.4.0 Objectives of the study

1. To study the status of student's techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.

“Techno Pedagogy In Education”

2. To study the student’s techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of standard nine in terms of gender.
3. To study the relationship between achievement in mathematics and techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.
4. To study the relationship of social attitude in techno-based mathematical learners and non-techno based mathematics learners of standard 9th.

1.5.0 Hypotheses of the study

Ho 1: There is no significant difference between the techno-based education attitude of boys and girls of 9th standard students towards learning mathematics.

Ho2: There is no relationship between techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics and achievement in mathematics of 9th standard students

Ho3: The social attitude of techno-based mathematical learners is significantly higher than non-techno based mathematics learners of standard 9th.

1.6.0 Methodology

In line with Hourigan, Leavy, and Carroll’s (2016) view that there is no single instrument that can guarantee the complete truth, a parallel convergent mixed research approach was adopted in our research. The present study was a descriptive survey on the social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students. The research was conducted in five phases and it is given in table 1.6.1

Table 1.6.1 Research Design

Phase 1	Selection of the variables involved in the study
Phase 2	Study of the related literature
Phase 3	Selection of the standardized tool to measure the carriable ICT education attitude towards learning mathematics
Phase 4	Collection of Data
Phase 5	Analysis and interpretation of data

1.7.0 Variables of the study

Three variables were selected. i.e

- i) Social attitude

- ii) Techno-based mathematics learning
- iii) Non-techno based mathematics learning

1.8.0 Tools used in the study

Sodhi’s Attitude Scale (SAS) constructed and standardized by Dr. Sodhi.was used

1.9.0 Population of the study

All the standard nine students who are studying in Kozhikode city in Kerala who study state syllabus

1.9.1 Sample of the study

The sample of the study included 100 students of class 9th.

- b. Area: Urban
- c. Number of schools: two
- d. Number of students: 100
- e. Gender: Girls and Boys
- f. Strata: 2 (Girls and Boys)
- g. Type of schools: Government aided.
- h. Medium: Malayalam

1.10.0 Procedure for data collection

To conduct the study the investigator selected Sodhi’s Attitude Scale (SAS) constructed by Dr. Sodhi. The test comprises of subsets viz.. Attitude towards teachers and parents, Attitude towards discipline, Attitude towards life and humanity, Attitude towards country, Attitude towards religion with a sixth component, Attitude towards society. The draft of the test containing 100 items was prepared covering five different sub-tests. Word processing, spread sheets, presentation tools, E-mailing and internet browsing. Necessary instructions and directions were worked for the entire five sub-tests. A separate response sheet and scoring key were also prepared. Following this, the test was carried out on a sample of 100 students of class 9th of St. Michael’s Girls, HSS, West hill and St. Joseph’s Boys HSS in Kozhikode District. The test was done in order to

- (i) Obtain objective information of each and every item

- (ii) Arrange the selected items in ascending order of difficulty and
- (iii) Fix up the time limit for each sub-test.

The pupils were given enough time to complete the test. They were clearly instructed how to attempt the items for all the five subtests.

1.11.0 Statistical techniques used in the study

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used to analyse and interpret the data. In the present study the statistical techniques such as Mean, standard deviation, ‘t’ test and Karl Pearson’s product moment correlation ‘r’ value was calculated.

1.12.0 Analysis of the objectives

The presentation of the results and their interpretation has been done objective wise.

1.12.1 Analysis of objective One

The first objective of the study was the status of student’s techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores on student’s techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.

Table1.1: showing the frequencies of the scores on student’s techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.

Level	Number of students	Percentage
Positive	89	89%
Neutral	8	8%
Negative	3	3%

As per the tool Range of ICT education attitude level was mentioned below.

Positive: 64 – 100; Neutral: 57 – 63; Negative : below 57

From the above table 1.1, it is concluded that 89% of students showed positive techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics, 8% students have neutral techno-based education

attitude towards learning mathematic and 3% students showed negative techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics.

Thus, it is concluded that majority of ninth standard students exhibited a high positive level of techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics.

1.12.2 Analysis of objective Two

The second objective of the study was to find the student’s techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of standard nine in terms of gender. In order to check the significance of this difference null hypothesis was formulated as;

H_0 : There is no significant difference in techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of ninth standard boys and girls.

The analysis and interpretation of the data related to this hypothesis was done with Mean, standard deviation, and ‘t’ test. The result has been presented in table 1.2

Table 1.2: Summary of N, Mean, SD, t-value of the scores of techno-based attitude towards learning mathematics of standard nine in terms of Gender.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Result
Boys	50	13.72	6.86	1.337	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	50	15.2	7.73		

From the above table 1.2, it reveals that calculated ‘t’ value is less than the table value. Therefore, null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference between the techno-based education attitudes of boys and girls of 9th standard students towards learning mathematics.

Thus, it is concluded that both boys and girls do not differ in their techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics.

1.12.3 Analysis of objective three

The third objective of the study was to find out the relationship between achievement in mathematics and techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

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In order to check the significance of this difference null hypothesis was formulated as:

Ho2: There is no relationship between techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics and achievement in mathematics of 9th standard students

The analysis and interpretation of the data related to this hypothesis was done with Mean, standard deviation, and ‘r’ value. The result has been presented in table 1.3

Table 1.3: Summary of N, Mean, SD, ‘r’ value of the scores of achievement in mathematics and techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	‘r’ value	‘t’ value	Remarks
Techno-based education attitude towards learning Mathematics	100	56.35	6.01	0.539	6.61	Significant at 0.05 level
Achievement in Mathematics	100	62.4	7.3			

From the above table 1.3, it is clear that the calculated ‘t’ value (6.61) is greater than the table value (1.96) significance at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

Thus, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between achievement in mathematics and techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

1.12.4 Analysis of objective four

Table 1.4: Summary of N, Mean, SD, ‘t’ value of the scores of social attitude of techno-based mathematical learners and non-techno based mathematics learners of standard 9th.

Variable	Group	Mean	SD	‘t’	Remarks
Attitude towards parents and teachers	Techno-based mathematics learners	1.479	3.359	3.28	Significant at 0.05 level
	Non-techno based mathematics learners	3.76	3.559		

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Attitude towards discipline	Techno-based mathematics learners	4.01	2.825	3.55	Significant at 0.05 level
	Non-techno based mathematics learners	3.8	3.357		
Attitude towards life and humanity	Techno-based mathematics learners	5.045	6.12	.036	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Non-techno based mathematics learners	5.08	4.82		
Attitude towards country	Techno-based mathematics learners	4.835	3.5	0.538	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Non-techno based mathematics learners	4.475	3.169		
Attitude towards religion	Techno-based mathematics learners	5.98	5.838	0.689	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Non-techno based mathematics learners	6.73	5.17		
Social attitude	Techno-based mathematics learners	21.459	12.27	0.98	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Non-techno based mathematics learners	23.89	12.559		

The table 1.4 shows that the mean, SD and t-ratio of the score of subject’s social attitude towards parent and teachers, discipline, life and humanity, country and religion between techno-based mathematics learners and non techno based mathematics learners. There was significant difference

in attitude towards parents and teachers among the techno-based mathematics learners and non techno based mathematics learners. There was significant difference shown in attitude towards discipline. There is no significant difference shown towards life and humanity, towards country and religion among the techno-based mathematics learners and non techno based mathematics learners. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

1.13.0 Major findings of the study

1. The majority of ninth standard students exhibited a high positive level of techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics.
2. Both boys and girls do not differ in their techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics.
3. There is a significant difference between achievement in mathematics and techno-based education attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.
4. There was significant difference in attitude towards parents and teachers among the techno-based mathematics learners and non techno based mathematics learners. There was significant difference shown in attitude towards discipline. There is no significant difference shown towards life and humanity, towards country and religion among the techno-based mathematics learners and non techno based mathematics learners of standard 9th.

1.14.0 Educational implications and recommendations of the study of social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students

In the present study, social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students was studied by the investigator. Based on the study, the following recommendations were given to develop more favourable social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students.

The findings of our study showed that with help of social attitude, techno-based mathematical learning can be flourished and students’ mathematical ability and rationalisation of thought can be enriched. It could be attributed to the home computer ownership among students, which may have contributed their Information Technology attitudes in a positive direction

- A large number of computer teachers needs to be appointed for successful implementation

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of techno-base in education.

- Government schools particularly of rural region should be facilitated more towards the implementation of techno-based education.
- High quality training of teachers is required regularly because technologies are invented every day.
- Increased encouragement should be provided for teachers who are willing to use computers in their subjects.

1.15.0 Suggestions for further research

The following are the suggestions for research in the future:

- ❖ The present study was conducted with a sample of 100 students. The same study can be conducted with large samples.
- ❖ The present study was restricted to only 9th standard students. It can be extended to other classes also.
- ❖ The present study was conducted in Kozhikode district in Kerala state. The study can be replicated on other districts of Kerala state.
- ❖ The present study can also be conducted at other levels of school education also.
- ❖ A comparative study can be done to know the difference between government and private school students, general and reserved category students.

1.16.0 Limitations of the study

- The sample was limited. The same study can be conducted with large number of samples.
- The present study was restricted to students of 9th standard in Kozhikode city.
- The study was restricted to two government aided schools of Kozhikode city.
- The study was restricted to the variables i.e., Social attitude, Techno-based mathematics learning and Non-techno based mathematics learning.
- The study was conducted in very small area.

Conclusion

The present study aimed at analyzing the social attitude in techno-based mathematical learning and non-techno based mathematics learning of 9th standard students with special variables like

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Social attitude, Techno-based mathematics learning and Non-techno based mathematics learning. The study indicates that there is significant differences and relationship between the variables.

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